

The influence of sustainability and digitalisation on business model innovation: The case of a multi-sided platform for food surplus redistribution[☆]

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ABSTRACT

While digital multi-sided platforms have been primarily investigated from a technical or economic perspective, the evolution of their business models over time and the significance of social and environmental sustainability for their success received relatively less attention. Through a longitudinal case study on the evolution of a digital platform for food surplus redistribution, we analyse how the business model of a multi-sided platform evolved to balance and integrate the objectives of economic viability with social and environmental sustainability goals. Data were collected through interviews with the platform stakeholders and then coded following the Gioia methodology. By adopting the lens of sociotechnical theory, we develop a set of four propositions to provide a generalisation of our findings to the broader literature on digital multi-sided platforms. Based on the results, we argue that the sustainable business model innovation process of a digital multi-sided platform must consider the mutual influence between business model innovation, sustainability dimensions internal to the business model, and the leverage of opportunities offered by digital technologies. Eventually, we underline the fundamental role of the platform leader in guiding such evolutionary process and its ability to generate benefits for all stakeholders through both sustainability and digitalisation levers.

1. Introduction

In the last two decades, the advancement of digital technologies and the diffusion of the sharing economy have enabled the development of a multitude of successful digital multi-sided platforms, such as Airbnb, Amazon, and Uber (Michellini, Principato, & Iasevoli, 2018; Muzellec, Ronteau, & Lambkin, 2015; Trabucchi & Buganza, 2020; Trabucchi, Buganza, Muzellec, & Ronteau, 2021). These platforms bring together two or more distinct, but interdependent, groups of customers and create value as intermediaries by allowing direct interactions between such customer sides (Muzellec et al., 2015). According to Muzellec et al. (2015), in order to remain competitive, these platforms' business models and marketing strategy orientation need to evolve over time. Similarly, Doz and Kosonen (2010) pointed out that "many [of these] companies fail, not because they do something wrong or badly, but because they

keep doing what used to be the right thing for too long and fall victim to the rigidity of their business model" (p. 370). However, despite a high level of academic interest in digital platforms, there is still little understanding on "the dynamics of platform-based business models, how they are built, and how they evolve over time across an extensive network of actors" (Kapoor et al., 2021, p. 102). In addition to this, in the business model literature, social and environmental sustainability is considered a key issue (Bocken, Short, Rana, & Evans, 2014), but it is only marginally connected with the topic of multi-sided platforms. Indeed, the primary focus of the literature on multi-sided platforms has been on the economic viability of the company's business model (Muzellec et al., 2015; Trabucchi et al., 2021; Trabucchi, Moretto, Buganza, & MacCormack, 2020; Zhao, von Delft, Morgan-Thomas, & Buck, 2020). Moreover, there has been relatively little research focused on environmental and social sustainability, and it is still not clear how

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sustainability can be a driver for both economic sustainability and business model innovation.

According to Franceschelli, Santoro, and Candelo (2018), digital technologies enable the introduction of business models that incorporate environmental, social, and economic concerns. An important context of application is represented by the food sector, where new technologies prevent and reduce food loss and waste (FLW) (Alfiero, Christofi, & Bonadonna, 2019; do Stangherlin, Duarte Ribeiro, & Barcellos, 2019; Trevisan & Formentini, 2023). Indeed, one of the most ground-breaking business models in the food industry is the development of food-sharing web platforms and/or mobile applications, which have proven to be effective in reducing edible food waste (Harvey, Smith, Goulding, & Branco Illodo, 2020). Globally, about one-third of all food produced is lost or wasted along the entire food supply chain, equivalent to 1.3 billion tons per year (Global food losses and food waste, 2011) resulting in about 2.6 trillion dollars of economic, social and environmental impacts yearly (FAO, 2014). Food sharing platforms (Ciulli, Kolk, & Boe-Lillegraven, 2020; Di Leo, Michelini, & Principato, 2020; Michelini et al., 2018; Mullick, Raassens, Haans, & Nijssen, 2021) have been increasingly popular in recent years and typically aim to reduce FLW and food poverty through food surplus redistribution (Thapa Karki, Bennett, & Mishra, 2021). The literature on food redistribution platforms has primarily focused on describing and classifying food sharing models and multi-sided platforms, or on investigating the features and aspects of food sharing business models (Amaral & Orsato, 2022; Ciulli et al., 2020; de Almeida Oroski, 2020; Michelini et al., 2018; Sarti, Corsini, Gusmerotti, & Frey, 2017), with only a few studies providing an in-depth understanding and a critical analysis of the evolution of digital platforms business model in this context (e.g., Di Leo et al., 2020). Moreover, as far as we know, none of them analyses how sustainability goals are addressed, influencing the transformation of the business model. This research gap results in a limited understanding of how digital multi-sided platforms integrate and balance different sustainability dimensions in their business model, and how they are able to be financially sustainable in a complex and competitive market. In response to these gaps, the main aim of this study is to investigate the evolution of a multi-sided platform's business model, balancing the objectives of economic sustainability with social and environmental sustainability goals.

We analyse the case of Regusto, a digital multi-sided platform founded in 2016 with the aim of reducing FLW through the redistribution of surplus food. This organisation managed to balance both business model innovation and a “triple bottom line” perspective on sustainability (Formentini & Taticchi, 2016). Moreover, through this case study, we seek to understand how different stakeholders connect and interact with the platform and its technology. In doing that, we adopt the perspective of digital multi-sided platforms as sociotechnical phenomena, through the lens of socio-technical theory (Haki, 2021; Kapoor et al., 2021), providing a practical example and a theoretical elaboration of their ability to evolve over time and innovate their business model for achieving socially, environmentally, and economically sustainable outcomes. Specifically, this study seeks to fill the aforementioned gaps by answering the following research question: *how does the business model of a digital multi-sided platform evolve over time to balance and integrate the objectives of economic sustainability with social and environmental sustainability goals?*

Eventually, we develop a set of propositions to provide a generalisation of our findings to the broader literature on digital multi-sided platforms.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. In Section 2, we review the literature on digital multi-sided platforms, introducing food redistribution platforms that aim to reduce FLW, as well as provide an overview of the literature on business model innovation and sustainable business model innovation. We then present our research question on the basis of the identified literature gaps. Section 3 introduces the research design and provides the background on the selected case study.

Section 4 presents in detail the findings of our study, firstly by describing the evolution of the Regusto platform and then explaining in detail the results that emerged from the coding process. In Section 5, we present our emerging theoretical framework and we develop four theoretical propositions. The final section concludes the paper, with the contributions to the academic literature and implications for practitioners, limitations and future research opportunities.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. Digital multi-sided platforms and business model innovation

Advances in information and communication technologies have paved the way for the development of a multitude of digital platforms. These platforms are intermediaries that enable the interactions between two or more distinct but interconnected “sides” (Evans & Noel, 2008; Filistrucchi, Geradin, van Damme, & Affeldt, 2014; Hagiú & Wright, 2015; Muzellec et al., 2015; Trabucchi et al., 2020). Depending on the number of involved stakeholders, platforms can be two-sided or multi-sided (Eisenmann, Parker, & Alstyne, 2006; Rochet & Tirole, 2006; Schmidt, Petzold, Lahme-Hütig, & Tiemann, 2021). By linking these sides, platforms generate “indirect or cross-side network externalities amongst various groups of customers” (Trabucchi et al., 2020 p. 7), meaning the platform's value depends on the number of users in each side (Rochet & Tirole, 2006; Roson, 2005). The existence of the cross-side network (or indirect) externalities between the sides is a fundamental element for the sustained functioning of multi-sided platforms (Armstrong, 2006; Caillaud & Jullien, 2003; de Reuver, Sørensen, & Basole, 2018; Evans, 2003; Evans & Noel, 2008; Loux, Aubry, Tran, & Baudoin, 2020). Besides this, multi-sided platforms generally promote the active involvement and co-production (i.e., the simultaneous production and consumption) of the sides they connect (Xie, Bagozzi, & Troye, 2008).

Indeed, it is essential to note that the concept of a business model itself emphasises the necessity of adapting, responding, and progressively driving the dynamics of digital transformation (Fürstenau, Klein, Vogel, & Auschra, 2021). A business model is a conceptual tool concerning how a firm commercialises a product or a technology, and how it creates, delivers, and captures value for all stakeholders (Casadesu-Masanell & Ricart, 2010; Chesbrough, 2010; Osterwalder, Pigneur, & Clark, 2010; Osterwalder, Pigneur, & Tucci, 2005). A business model is composed of three elements: (i) the value proposition; (ii) the value creation and delivery; and (iii) the value capture (Chesbrough, 2002; Teece, 2010; Beltramello, 2013).

Based on the above, business model innovation consists of both the creation of a new business model and improving and adjusting one or more of its elements (Geissdoerfer, 2018; Osterwalder et al., 2010), such as its value proposition or the logic of value creation (Bocken et al., 2014). More specifically, Foss and Saebi, (2017, p. 201) define business model innovation as “designed, novel, nontrivial changes to the key elements of a firm's business model and/or the architecture linking these elements”. These changes can lead to the creation of a new business model (Osterwalder et al., 2005), to the transition from one business model to another, to the reconfiguration or diversification into additional business models (Aversa, Formentini, Iubatti, & Lorenzoni, 2021; Aversa, Furnari, & Haefliger, 2015), or to the acquisition of new business models (Geissdoerfer, 2018; Massa & Tucci, 2014). In this sense, business model innovation contributes to creating new markets, helps businesses thrive in the current competitive environment, provides new social values, and can be a vehicle for diversification and innovation (Geissdoerfer, 2018; Thompson & MacMillan, 2010).

By extending the concept of business model innovation into the context of multi-sided platforms, existing literature argues that platforms' business model and marketing strategy orientation need to evolve over time to maintain a competitive position in the market (Muzellec et al., 2015; Rolland, Mathiasen, & Rai, 2018; Zhao et al.,

2020). Indeed, continuous adaptation, innovation, and change in the business model are necessary for firms to remain relevant (Hacklin, Björkdahl, & Wallin, 2018; Wirtz, Schilke, & Ullrich, 2010).

As shown in Fig. 1, research on multi-sided platforms has primarily focused on their business strategy (Alstyn et al., 2016; Mancha & Gordon, 2022), platform ecosystems (Ceccagnoli et al., 2012; Cozzolino et al., 2021; Jacobides et al., 2018; Parker et al., 2016), business model structure (Muzellec et al., 2015), platform architecture (Kapoor et al., 2021), and disruptive innovation (Kazan, 2018; Schmidt et al., 2021), with an emphasis on economic sustainability (Muzellec et al., 2015; Trabucchi et al., 2020; Zhao et al., 2020) rather than on environmental and social sustainability. Consumer-to-consumer (C2C) and business-to-consumer (B2C) platforms have received more attention (Loux et al., 2020), while business-to-business (B2B) platforms have been less studied. Moreover, although there is a significant academic interest concerning multi-sided platform business models (Di Leo et al., 2020; Fürstenau et al., 2021; Muzellec et al., 2015; Sarti et al., 2017; Zhao et al., 2020), there is still a lack of knowledge regarding the dynamics of innovation of multi-sided platform business models, namely how they are created and how they evolve and innovate (Kapoor et al., 2021). Finally, studies that adopt a longitudinal, process-based case study method are far scarcer (Haki, 2021), as well as studies adopting a clear theoretical lens.

In light of this, our research is embedded in the theme of a multi-sided platform business model, but it focuses on the business model innovation process of such platform, thus introducing the elements of evolution of the business model over time, specifically in the B2B sector and potentially involving other stakeholders.

2.2. Sustainable business model innovation and food-sharing platforms: Balancing social, environmental and economic sustainability

Due to their significant control over resources and capabilities, companies are recognised as central actors in addressing sustainability

challenges (Porter & Kramer, 2011).

Consequently, the concept of value creation of businesses has evolved to incorporate social and environmental objectives alongside economic goals (De Bernardi, Bertello, & Forliano, 2021; Schaltegger, Hansen, & Lüdeke-Freund, 2016), encompassing a triple bottom line approach and considering a broader range of stakeholder interests (Freudenreich, Lüdeke-Freund, & Schaltegger, 2020; Laasch, 2018; Massa, Tucci, & Afuah, 2017). Therefore, business models need to evolve by incorporating sustainability dimensions (Boldrini & Antheaume, 2021), leading to the concept of sustainable business model innovation (SBMI) (Boons & Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; Schaltegger, Lüdeke-Freund, & Hansen, 2011; Yang, Evans, Vladimirova, & Rana, 2017). SBMI which is defined “as innovation to create positive impacts, and significantly reduced negative impacts for the environment and society, through changes in the way the organisation and its value-network create, deliver and capture value or change their value propositions” (Bocken & Geradts, 2020, p. 2). However, despite such opportunities, it remains unclear how such changes occur and if and how companies can produce economic value through sustainability (Schaltegger et al., 2011).

Within the context of digital multi-sided platforms, (Kolk & Ciulli, 2020; Schanes & Stagl, 2019) several studies (Mattila, Mesiranta, & Heikkinen, 2020; Mazzucchelli, Gurioli, Graziano, Quacquarelli, & Aouina-Mejri, 2021; Michelini et al., 2018; Michelini, Grieco, Ciulli, & Di Leo, 2020; Mu, Spaargaren, & Oude Lansink, 2019; Schroder, Prockl, & Constantiou, 2021; Secondi, Principato, & Mattia, 2019) have highlighted food-sharing platforms as exemplars of sustainable business model, due to their capacity to offer multiple value propositions encompassing economic, social, and environmental benefits (de Almeida Oroski & da Silva, 2022).

These platforms represent innovative business models that effectively address the adverse environmental consequences of excess food while also contributing to poverty alleviation (Ciulli et al., 2020; Michelini et al., 2018), leveraging food surplus redistribution at various

Fig. 1. Graphical literature review of papers dealing with the macro areas of multi-sided platform and business model innovation, underlining the main theme of each cluster of papers and the theoretical lens adopted.

stages of production, distribution, and food service.

These platforms can be broadly categorised into three models: (i) “sharing for money”, (ii) “sharing for charity” and (iii) “sharing for the community” (Michelini et al., 2018). The “sharing for money” model tends to be operated by for-profit organisations that operate exclusively online (pure-player) through website platforms or mobile applications. The delivery model for this type of platform is primarily B2C, so the food is collected from wholesalers or producers, who use a website or app to list unsold items, and the customer then purchases cheap food (online or directly in-store). The “sharing for charity” model is commonly operated by NPOs. Here, the delivery model is primarily B2B since food is collected from various suppliers and is offered at no cost to non-profit entities on a local and national basis. The “sharing for the community” model is operated by for-profit or non-profit organisations that operate exclusively through web platforms and apps using a peer-to-peer (P2P) delivery model, whereby food is gathered from consumers and shared with other consumers on a local basis, with the primary goal of benefiting a community (Michelini et al., 2018).

In light of these considerations, it is widely acknowledged that food-sharing platforms play a crucial role in promoting sustainability by addressing issues such as waste reduction, social inclusion, and community engagement. However, despite the fact that social and environmental sustainability goals are central to the platforms’ value proposition, their actual impact on these areas is often unclear (Michelini et al., 2020). Moreover, research suggests that only the “sharing for money” platforms often reach economic sustainability (Michelini et al., 2018) while those belonging to the other two categories usually incorporate social and environmental sustainability goals as part of their business model (Mattila et al., 2020), but typically struggle to achieve economic profitability, especially in the long term. As a result, while digital platforms are able to address FLW, they often struggle to evolve towards financially stable business model configurations or may eventually fail. Indeed, most are in their early stages of development, and their business models are still in the experimentation phase (De Almeida Oroski & Da Silva, 2023).

Despite the emergence of new business models based on the sharing economy, academic literature exploring these platforms is still limited (Di Leo et al., 2020). Only a limited number of studies offer an in-depth understanding of the evolution of food-sharing platforms’ business model (e.g. Di Leo et al., 2020). In light of these challenges and limitations, there is a critical need for further research to explore how digital multi-sided platforms integrate and balance different sustainability dimensions in their business model, and how they are able to be economically sustainable in a complex and competitive market. Given the impact that food sector has at the social and environmental level, we investigate the aforementioned gaps in the context of a digital multi-sided platform for food surplus redistribution.

2.3. Digital multi-sided platforms as socio-technical phenomena

Digital multi-sided platforms are characterised by a core technological component enabling the interactions between two or more sides of users. To better understand the interaction occurring among the technological core and the users’ side, thus the social side of the digital platform, we draw upon sociotechnical theory. Sociotechnical theory builds on the idea that “the design and performance of an organisation can be understood only when the social and technical aspects are considered in conjunction and treated as interdependent elements of a complex system” (Kapoor et al., 2021 p. 95). Sociotechnical theory has been adopted by scholars to understand complex systems across different fields, such as manufacturing and production (Baxter & Somerville, 2011), to understand interactions between humans and machines. Sociotechnical systems contain social elements, such as people organisations and institutions, and technical elements, which co-exist. The continuous interaction among these two elements determines a series of alternating system configurations of balance and unbalance,

prompting the entire system towards transformation and evolution over time (Amir & Kant, 2018; Kapoor et al., 2021; Lytinen & Newman, 2008; Rolland et al., 2018), thus recalling the aforementioned concept of business model innovation. According to sociotechnical theory, organisations are considered as systems of four interacting and aligned components: tasks, actors, structure, and technology:

- *Structure* covers systems of communication, systems of authority, and systems of workflow. It includes both the normative dimension, and the behavioural dimension.
- *Technology* includes all elements of the organisation’s technological core covering production, distribution and R&D technologies.
- *Task* describes the organisation’s *raison d’être* and the way in which it orients towards and adapts to its environment and meets the requirements and constraints of its different stakeholders.
- *Actors* include any individual or group that has a stake or can set up a requirement towards the organisation.

Any variation in any of these components can determine a structural misalignment, named gap, which needs to be mitigated to control and maintain the system overall equilibrium. An example of event generating a change in one component is the introduction of a new technological tool, or the change in the management of a company (Leavitt, 1964), which determines a change in the other components.

Recently, scholars have been considering digital platforms through a sociotechnical lens (de Reuver et al., 2018; Haki, 2021; Kapoor et al., 2021; Rolland et al., 2018). This lens is ideal for digital multi-sided platforms, as they are characterised by a technological architecture that attracts a variety of actors, allowing the exchange of goods, services, and data and thus enabling value co-creation for both the platform itself, its stakeholders, and the entire business ecosystem.

Therefore, the sociotechnical model described by Lytinen and Newman (2008) has been adapted by Kapoor et al. (2021) to fit digital multi-sided platforms, as represented in Fig. 2.

As mentioned in paragraph 2.1, the technical and structural aspects have been widely investigated in platforms literature (Kapoor et al., 2021; Staub, Haki, Aier, Winter, & Magan, 2021), by focusing for instance on their architecture, technology and modules (e.g. Tiwana, Konsynski, & Bush, 2010), at the expense of the social dimension. Moreover, the research agenda proposed by Kapoor et al. (2021) calls for further research that highlights the overlap and mutual influence between the four sociotechnical dimensions of technology, structure, actors and task, that are constantly interacting with each other. Furthermore, we follow the suggestion of Kapoor et al. (2021), Haki (2021) and Rolland et al. (2018) to study how a digital multi-sided platform’s business model consequently evolves over time.

3. Research design

In order to investigate our research question, we had the opportunity to access and analyse the evolution of the business model of Regusto, a food redistribution platform created in 2016. Regusto has an “exemplar” model of digitalisation and sustainability of food surplus redistribution activities, i.e., “organisations that are well ahead of their industry on either social and/or environmental performance while still maintaining economic viability” (Pagell & Wu, 2009, p.40). As such, Regusto serves a representative case, that allows us to develop a meaningful understanding of our phenomenon of interest, as highlighted in Siggelkow’s seminal article Siggelkow (2007). Following the suggestion of Haki (2021), we perform a longitudinal, process-based case study of Regusto’s platform evolution, to develop a persuasive and detailed theoretical understanding of its business model innovation.

3.1. Empirical setting

As a result of the growing attention on FLW prevention and reduction

Fig. 2. Representation of the four components of a platform according to the sociotechnical lens. Adapted from (Kapoor et al., 2021).

practices, food sharing platforms have been increasingly popular in recent years (Ciulli et al., 2020; Di Leo et al., 2020; Michelini et al., 2018; Mullick et al., 2021). An example is MyFoody, an Italian B2C platform that allows food manufacturers and retailers to offer products near their expiration date to customers, thus preventing FLW and offering reduced food prices for customers. FoodCloud is a non-profit corporation with the aim of tackling FLW by providing companies with a convenient opportunity for donating excess food to charities in their areas. Finally, Olio, allows users to share foods that are close to the expiration date. All these platforms prioritise the reduction of FLW through different mechanisms but follow a pre-established path since they usually evolve towards very similar business models, and frequently limited to the downstream supply chain with a P2P or B2C delivery model.

3.1.1. Case study introduction

There is a multitude of different platforms with the aim of reducing and/or preventing FLW and all have tended to follow a similar “institutionalised” path. Unlike these platforms, Regusto is an interesting example because the company was able to sustain the continued evolution of its business model over time, offering increased value to its customers in terms of digitalisation and sustainability dimensions. Beyond the FLW context, Regusto expanded into the non-food sector, thus opening up for further discussion and more generalisable results.

3.1.2. Data collection

This study relies on 14 semi-structured interviews with 8 different stakeholders of the Regusto platform, conducted between March 2022 and September 2022 (see Table 1 for an overview of the sample). Initially, we were addressing exclusively the platform provider to map

the business model evolution and interviewed the co-founder of Regusto. We shortly recognised the importance of including the supply side, the demand side, and the non-transactional side of the platform (Fili-Strucchi et al., 2014; Trabucchi et al., 2020). One interview with the blockchain technology provider of Regusto was then included in order to build a comprehensive understanding of all the key actors in the platform ecosystem.

We performed semi-structured interviews, adapting the scope of the investigation according to the type of respondent. For instance, our interviews with the COO and Co-founder of Recuperiamo s.r.l. gave us the opportunity to ask detailed questions about the key features characterising the different business models over time to better understand the determinants of such business model evolution. Interviews with the platform’s sides (i.e., supply and demand sides) were focused on why and when the partnership with Regusto started, how the partnership has been managed so far, and what are the advantages and disadvantages of the partnership. Respondents were also asked to define their concept of social and environmental sustainability, and whether it changed over time. We integrated interviews with secondary information (start-up and platform information, website, etc.) to develop a more comprehensive understanding of our context and ensure the reliability of data.

3.1.3. Data analysis

We combined methods for a single, longitudinal case study (Eisenhardt, 1989; Van de Ven & Poole, 1990) with the Gioia methodology (Gioia, Corley, & Hamilton, 2013). Doing so allowed us to trace the evolution of Regusto and generalise emerging findings to similar types of platforms. The analysis was conducted iteratively: as new insights were emerging, we conducted additional rounds of data collection and analysis. For the sake of clarity and transparency, we illustrate this process

Table 1
Sample description.

Informant	Type of firm	Interviewees	Number of interviews	Interviews duration
Co-founder of Regusto	Platform provider	COO and Co-founder of Recuperiamo s.r.l.	5	4 h 36 m
Informant 1	Blockchain technology provider	Business Developer Europe Director	1	28 m
Informant 2	Third sector organisation	Solidarity Emporium manager Projects and fundraising manager	1	1 h
Informant 3	Private company (donor of non-food items)	CSR manager	2	40 m
Informant 4	Private company (donor of food items)	CSR manager	2	1 h
Informant 5	Third sector organisation	Partnerships’ manager	1	30 m
Informant 6	Private company (credits acquirer)	Business owner	1	20
Informant 7	Municipality	Council member	1	20 m
			Total duration	8 h 54 m

Table 2
Timeline of evolution of Regusto platform (graphical elements adapted from (Trabucchi & Buganza, 2020).

Regusto's business model in a specific time period	Key events	Value proposition, customer segments and revenues streams evolution description
<p>Business model (a): The beginning as a traditional food surplus redistribution platform</p> <p>(a) 2016</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regusto was founded as a B2C app for redistributing restaurants' food surplus. 	<p>Value proposition: offer customers excess meals from restaurants at a discounted price.</p> <p>Customer segments: Restaurants, bars; private users.</p> <p>Revenue streams: percentage of sales.</p>
<p>Business model (b): The expansion towards the upstream supply chain</p> <p>(b) 2018</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Entrance of new and stronger competitors in the market. Development of B2B model to be tested in parallel with the initial B2C model. Introduction of blockchain technology in 2019. 	<p>Value proposition: collect food surplus from the food supply chain and redistribute it to charities.</p> <p>Customer segments: Municipalities; Companies; Charities.</p> <p>Revenue streams: fee for municipalities for obtaining transparent data about food surplus redistribution activities and for optimising environmental policies.</p>
<p>Business model (c): The B2B model</p> <p>(c) 2020</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The growing competition in the market and the crisis impacting the food service sector during the Covid-19 pandemic spurred the evolution of the business model from a B2C towards a full B2B model. In 2021, the platform, included the donation and selling of non-food products. Companies such as Leroy Merlin and Samsung joined the platform for donating or selling unsold furniture, electronic, and domestic appliances. 	<p>Value proposition: collect food (and non-food items) surplus from the food supply chain and redistribute it to charities.</p> <p>Customer segments: Municipalities; Companies; Charities.</p> <p>Revenue streams: fee on the kilograms of food and items donated or sold by companies and annual subscription fee.</p>
<p>Business model (d): The credits-based business model</p> <p>(d) 2022</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; margin-top: 10px;"> <p>Data flow → Revenue flow → Possible revenue flow →</p> <p>Credits flow → Possible credits flow → Goods flow →</p> </div>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The final evolution of the platform consisted in the generation of exchangeable credits through food and non-food donations. In this new scenario, a new side made-up of companies acquiring credits is called to interact with the platform, and the business model evolved consequently. 	<p>Value proposition: collect food (and non-food items) surplus from the food supply chain and redistribute it to charities.</p> <p>Customer segments: Municipalities; Companies (donors); Companies (purchasing credits); Charities.</p> <p>Revenue streams: the economic model changed, as companies donating goods were not charged with a fee on transactions and revenues streams stemmed from the acquisition of credits performed by other companies.</p>

sequentially in the following steps.

Step 1. Longitudinal reconstruction of events – For this step, we drew upon the interviews conducted with the COO and Co-founder of Recuperiamo s.r.l. to establish how the Regusto platform's business model evolved over time. We established the turning-points of the business model evolution, trying to understand the contextual factors and the motivations behind such changes in the business model structure. For each stage in this timeline, we reconstructed the economic model, unfolding costs and revenue streams, and the customer relationships. We also mapped the information exchange between the platform and its customers, as well as the flow of physical goods. The final output of this step was a timeline of the evolution of the platform, which is depicted in Table 2 in the Findings section.

Step 2. Data coding: building the data structure and the data table – For this step, data were collected through semi-structured interviews with the aforementioned respondents. These interviews were analysed according to the method developed by Gioia et al. (2013). We used NVivo

12 for the coding process. After importing the interview transcripts into NVivo, an in-depth reading of the interviews was conducted with the aim of identifying 1st Order Concepts. After initially coding about fifty concepts, similar concepts were grouped together and arranged into 18 1st Order Concepts. We then clustered these concepts into seven 2nd Order Themes, which were re-labelled multiple times in order to capture the building blocks of our grounded model. We report a series of representative quotes for our each of our 1st Order Concepts and 2nd Order Themes in Table A1 in the Appendix section. We consequently investigated whether it was possible to abstract Aggregate Dimensions from the 2nd Order Themes, which together with the 1st Order Concepts, became the foundation for building a visual “data structure”, which lays at the basis for further considerations later in the theorising process. The resulting data structure is reported in Fig. 3 and analysed in detail in the Findings section.

Step 3. Development of the theoretical framework – For this step, following the methodology of Gioia et al. (2013), we combined the 2nd

Order Themes, showing the interrelationships among them in a grounded model, which is presented in the *Discussion* section.

4. Findings

This section is structured in two parts. First, we describe in detail the evolution of Regusto's business model over time, in order to clarify the temporal and contextual boundaries the case study. Second, we explain the data structure (Fig. 3) by "zooming-in" on each key emergent concept, drawing on informants' exemplars quotes to support each concept and ensure transparency in the data-to-theory connections.

4.1. The timeline of the evolution of Regusto's platform

Table 2 provides a pictorial analysis of the business model evolution over time, leveraging the graphical representation of a multi-sided platform adapted from Trabucchi and Buganza (2020).

4.2. Data structure: findings and analysis from the main themes

4.2.1. Sustainable business model innovation

Evidence emerging from the interviews on the changes of business model components suggests that the platform has undergone a business model innovation (Berends, Smits, Reymen, & Podoyntsyna, 2016; Haftor & Climent Costa, 2023). In Table 3, the evolution of the platform's customer segments clearly emerges: in 2016 (business model a) the supply side was composed of restaurants, bars, and local groceries, and the demand side of private users; after the shift towards the B2B (business model b-c), the supply and demand were composed of private food and non-food companies and charities, respectively, with an additional non-transactional side composed by municipalities. The typology of actors involved remained unchanged until 2022, when an additional non-transactional side joined the platform, made of companies purchasing credits.

The main changes occurred in the economic model, as outlined in Table 4. Such changes influenced the customer relationships, and, ultimately, the company's value proposition. In business model a), revenues stemmed from a fee on food surplus sales and purchase, while in business model b), the model changed, with revenues stemming from municipalities. The business model d) relied on revenues from the sale of sustainability credits. In fact, donating exceeding items implies avoiding CO₂ emissions, soil and water degradation and it generates a positive social impact in terms of redistributed meals. Such positive social and environmental impacts are measured and translated into credits, which are non-fungible tokens (NFT) recorded in blockchain. One credit corresponds to 1 equivalent meal donated, 0,5 Kg of avoided CO₂ emissions, 3m³ of water saved, and 10m² of land saved thanks to the donation of food and non-food products. The credits thus generated can be acquired both by donors themselves and by other companies to offset their environmental impacts and for supporting social sustainability initiatives, thus enabling the economic sustainability of the platform through the credits' monetisation. Any information regarding donations, credits generated and acquired is certified by a third party and it is collected in a public ledger in order to increase the transparency of the entire process.

As a result of these economic changes, different and evolving relationships with each customer segment were established. For instance, Regusto evolved from occasional transactions performed by private users to established and long-lasting partnerships with charities and donors. Finally, substantial changes at the value proposition level occurred. One significant example is the redistribution of non-food products.

In this context, digitalisation played a central role in the business model innovation process and on several occasions Regusto was able to leverage the opportunities offered by digital technologies. Indeed, digitalisation has been part of the core values of Regusto since their founding and the digitalisation of the entire donation process was a

recurring element in the interviews: "Since the beginning Regusto aimed at leveraging its digital assets and competences for enabling an innovative business model. Companies have recognised this feature of Regusto and they appreciate the possibility of managing digitally the donation process end-to-end, when, in most cases, such a process was previously managed manually" reports Regusto Co-founder. The platform was born as an app for private customers and, as the business model evolved, it now has the functionalities of a software application that brings users continuously improved digital functionalities. For example, introduced blockchain for ensuring the transparency of credits transactions.

Therefore, in parallel with the development of a novel value proposition, the technological element started to become a key resource of the business model. The platform was collecting a large amount of data on food donations and as such, the need for higher transactions transparency and traceability emerged, especially from the supply side: "We noticed that our clients were demanding higher standards in terms of transactions transparency, security and reliability, thus we introduced blockchain technology." (Co-founder of Regusto). The introduction of blockchain technology in 2019 represented the answer to such changing customer needs. However, the introduction of this technology did not have immediate implications at the business model level, as its initial aim was ensuring the security and traceability of donations transactions. In the final evolution of the business model the functionalities enabled by blockchain technology acquired greater importance. Indeed, the adoption of blockchain technology undoubtedly contributed to building and promoting a trustworthy, secure, and innovation-oriented image of customer companies and of the platform itself: "The desire to choose Regusto is also motivated by the use of blockchain which allows obtaining great value not only in terms of certified and transparent operations, but also in terms of brand image" (Informant 4).

Aside from the elements of business model innovation and technology, social, environmental and economic sustainability emerged as a prominent element in our interviews. Sustainability has been an embedded component of Regusto's business purpose and processes since its founding. However, in the initial business model the social and environmental sustainability claim was still in infancy, but it gained more and more importance as the business model evolved. Therefore, we crafted the theme "evolution of endogenous sustainability dimensions" to indicate the emerging concept of the progressive layering of social, environmental, and economic sustainability dimensions internal to the business model. Indeed, initially the platform was not providing customers with details on how their food redistribution activity impacted the environment, or addressing the social sustainability dimension, since charities were not the donation's recipients. Through the following stages of Regusto's evolution, the progressive layering of sustainability objectives clearly emerges. By addressing the non-profit sector rather than private customers the social sustainability dimension was finally included in the core business practices of the platform in 2020. In parallel, environmental sustainability objectives acquired progressively more relevance. In particular, the platform introduced the importance of measuring social and environmental impacts, starting from the measurement of equivalent meals redistributed, and later by measuring avoided CO₂ emissions, as well as land and water spoilage. The platform eventually developed a set of 18 new indicators to improve the measurement of the impact of avoided waste on society and on the environment, offering customers the opportunity for sustainability performance disclosure. Of course, to ensure the platform's success and sustained evolution, the economic sustainability dimension evolved as well, as illustrated in Table 4. While the revenue stream initially used a fee-based model, which depended on transactional relationships with occasional customers, it evolved towards a subscription model, aimed at establishing more secure and long-term relationships with professional customers.

4.2.2. External drivers of sustainable business model innovation

Interviewees suggested that contextual factors, such as market

Fig. 3. Data structure.

competition, and market and supply chain disruptions, played a role in fostering the business model innovation process: “The entrance in the market of a strong competitor with a comparable business model and, afterward, the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic are two factors that have led to an evolution of the platform business model. We decided to discontinue the app due to the crisis affecting the food service sector, while greater importance was given to the non-profit. After the pandemic, the platform tool for addressing the B2B sector was finally adopted, in order to respond to food requirements deriving from the health emergency” (Regusto Co-founder). For instance, the limited resources available during the pandemic forced the platform to change its revenue streams: Regusto moved from municipalities towards companies upstream in the agri-food food supply chain, thus re-inventing and expanding the service offered to the customers and, as a consequence, the value proposition.

In addition to contextual factors exogenous (i.e., external to the BM), external sustainability requirements emerged from our interviews as another driver of business model innovation. On multiple occasions, the Regusto platform was able to take advantage of sustainability opportunities that were overlooked by competitors in the market, as well as latent needs for more concrete sustainability actions that companies were starting to require. For instance, in the first development stages, the platform lacked the ability to measure the positive environmental

sustainability impact generated. The market soon started to require higher sustainability standards, asking for precise measurements of companies’ social and environmental footprint, as stated by Informant 6: “We have the objective of improving our sustainability positioning and performances, also, our clients are requiring higher sustainability standards.” Regusto responded to such market pressure by providing customers with the measurement of the impacts of donating food, both by measuring the number of donated meals and the avoided environmental impact. As a consequence, the social and environmental sustainability perspectives were reinforced and became part of the business model value proposition.

Regusto then included donations of non-food items. Informant 3 revealed that they joined the platform thanks to the company’s collaboration with policymakers, which resulted in the extension of the Italian law on the donation of food products (Law 166/16) to include non-food products. As a result, the platform introduced the possibility for non-food companies to donate excess products. This product scope extension represented a departure from other competing platforms that were exclusively focused on food surplus redistribution.

As such, two different perspectives on sustainability emerged during the coding process (i.e., those external and internal to the business model), we chose to differentiate among exogenous sustainability

Table 3
Evolution of Regusto’s customer segments over time.

		Evolution of customer segments			
		Business model a)	Business model b)	Business model c)	Business model d)
Regusto platform’s customers	Supply side	Food services	Food companies	Food and non-food companies	Food and non-food companies
	Demand side	Private users	Charities	Charities	Charities
	Non-transactional side	–	Municipalities	Municipalities	Municipalities and companies acquiring credits

Table 4
Evolution of Regusto’s economic model over time (detailed evolution of the revenue streams).

		Evolution of revenue streams			
		Business model a)	Business model b)	Business model c)	Business model d)
Regusto platform’s customers	Supply side	Fee on food surplus sales	–	Fee on food and non-food surplus donations / annual subscription fee	Potential purchase of sustainability credits
	Demand side	Fee on food surplus purchase	–	–	–
	Non-transactional side	–	Revenue flow from municipalities accessing food redistribution data	–	Purchase of credits performed by companies

requirements and endogenous sustainability dimensions. The first is related to sustainability objectives and practices that the external context requires of the platform, while the second refers to the economic, social, and environmental dimensions of the triple bottom line construct that has been internalised in the platform’s business model.

4.2.3. Benefits for platform’s stakeholders

Joining the Regusto platform enhanced technological performance and competencies for both customers and the Regusto platform, creating benefits for all of the platform’s stakeholders. Interviewees agreed that the platform’s ability to enable new partnerships and create new connections between donors and charities simplified the management of the donation process for both sides: “Regusto allows our company to access donations from new suppliers frequently coming from a different city or region, therefore Regusto has played an important role in creating contacts with new companies and reinforcing existing partnerships.” (Informant 5). “One of the main benefits of Regusto is the speed of finding third sector clients for quickly donating surplus products” (Informant 3). In addition to the ease of creating new networks of partners, the platform simplified the management of such relationships thanks to digitalisation of the entire donation process. Indeed, the second most important benefit mentioned by informants was the access to digital competencies, the digitalisation of donation processes and procedures, and the tracking and management of donated products in an easy and intuitive way. This was true especially for charities, which were usually characterised by limited resources to invest in digital assets and competencies but could access this service for free through Regusto. Donor companies reported the benefits of digitalisation as well: “Regusto allowed the agile and punctual measurement of data related to donations, simplifying the process of registering the donation on our systems” (Informant 4). The mutually beneficial effects of increased and enhanced sustainability performance also emerged from interviews. Both Regusto and its customers benefited from the ease of finding new donors and donations recipients, establishing a virtuous cycle: through the creation of new partnerships, charities could access donations of a variety of different products, and donors avoid additional disposal costs on surplus products, receiving in exchange the measurement of social and environmental impact achieved. In turn, the platform began to grow by extending the number of customers, thus incrementing the network effect and strengthening the platform’s economic sustainability. Regarding social and environmental sustainability, one of the customers’ most appreciated elements was the measurement of sustainability performance: the resulting indicators were characterised by high reliability and transparency, since the measurements of avoided impacts are certified by an

international entity, thus facilitating data disclosure through Corporate Sustainability Reports (CSR) or communication campaigns. Engaging in and communicating the results of concrete actions that enhanced companies’ sustainability performance was perceived as a competitive advantage, especially for companies aiming at hindering the “green-washing” phenomenon. Several customers recognised the importance of generating a positive impact within the territory in which they operated, which provided Regusto with a remarkable advantage. Such territorial impact of the platform was especially crucial for municipalities, who valued their partnership with Regusto, while also underlining the complexity element of dealing with GDPR compliance: “Having visibility on donation flow in our municipality is crucial since it gives us the possibility of building a comprehensive picture of solidarity and circularity initiatives in our territory, as well as promoting such initiatives also outside our territory borders, which is especially relevant in nowadays with water savings and CO₂” (Informant 7).

5. Discussion

Fig. 4 illustrates our grounded model, which depicts the relationships among the 2nd Order Themes presented in the data structure (Fig. 3). In the conceptual framework, sustainability emerges as the central element in the evolution of a digital multi-sided platform. Its influence is recognised at the business model level and externally to the business model domain, as part of the external drivers for sustainable business model innovation and among the benefits for the platform’s stakeholders. Similarly, the ability of the company to leverage digital technology opportunities is a key aspect of the business model innovation of a digital multi-sided platform, and has positive effects for all the platform’s stakeholders. However, a mutual influence exists among the leverage of digital opportunities and the evolution of sustainability dimensions endogenous to the business model; therefore, both of these aspects should be considered when referring to the SBMI of a digital multi-sided platform.

In order to reinforce the validity of our findings emerging from the coding process, in this section we review and discuss the grounded model through the lens of sociotechnical theory, thus we aim at contributing to the theory on digital multi-sided platforms as sociotechnical phenomena by building on the research agenda suggested by Kapoor et al. (2021). In doing that, we recall the four components of the sociotechnical theory presented in chapter 2.4 of actors, tasks technology and structure and we build four propositions. Moreover, we seek to expand the scope of sociotechnical theory, including the key role of

sustainability dimensions besides the technical and social components, which has been instead overlooked in previous studies. Reviewing our results through the lens of sociotechnical theory shows the interrelations among actors, tasks technology and structure, thus confirming the results of Kapoor et al. (2021), which underlines the complexity and mutual influence existing among each sociotechnical element. In particular, we analyse in depth the four most prominent findings of this study.

5.1. Effective platform leadership

The evolution of the platform structure and tasks is the result of the co-existence of top-down control and bottom-up emergence (Haki, 2021). Top-down control consists of establishing roles, standards, and principles in order to align actors’ behaviour with the objectives of the platform and of the corresponding business ecosystem. For instance, as reported in Table 2, Regusto intentionally decided to focus on the upstream part of the supply chain, targeting the B2B segment and moving away from the “institutionalised” path followed by the majority of similar food surplus redistribution apps. Top-down control is performed by the platform leader and it is a necessary, but insufficient mechanism to ensure structural stability. Digital platform also requires generativity, allowing bottom-up emergence of new roles and institutional arrangements among actors in response to external drivers of change. Generativity is possible due to the affordance of pervasive technologies, which are dynamic, malleable, and characterised by the capacity to produce change driven by large audiences (Yoo, Boland, Lyytinen, & Majchrzak, 2012). For example, the introduction of blockchain technology, as a response to initial market and customer requirements, became essential for generating and exchanging credits, thus enabling the creation of a novel platform structure. In the presented case, the platform leader shows the ability to individuate and capture signals from the context, such as the drivers of change in terms of market competition and exogenous sustainability requirements, and integrate them at the business model level, managing at the same time the technical core of the platform and its complexity. However, the integration of such external drivers requires to take into account the platform’s stakeholders desires and expectations. In doing this, the platform’s leader is responsible to create incentives for new customers to join the platform and to strengthen the relationship with existing customers. Therefore, platform leader plays a crucial role since it implements task-level actions that are triggered by external drivers and internalised at the business model level, to enable benefits for all stakeholders.

Our findings confirm the key role played by the platform’s leader in

internalising and integrating external drivers and sustainability requirements into the platform’s business model, thus changing its structure and tasks, filtering and balancing such factors to meets the platform’s strategy and stakeholder’s expectations.

Proposition 1. In order to achieve a successful platform positioning in the market, the platform leader should identify contextual factors and exogenous sustainability requirements and include them in the business model, filtering and balancing such factors with the objectives and expectations of all the platform’s stakeholders.

5.2. Dynamics of platform-based business models

Changes in policies and regulatory frameworks can significantly impact on the evolution of a platform’s structure and competitive strategy, thus re-arranging its business model to incorporate such changes (Kapoor et al., 2021). In the described case, changes in regulatory framework, but also in the competitive environment and customers’ expectations undoubtedly influenced the platform’s structure and its trajectory of evolution to accommodate such changes. For instance, higher sustainability standards to incentivise a business’s commitment in achieving social and environmental goals, or the introduction of non-food items redistribution consequent to the Covid-19 pandemic regulations impacted on different building blocks of the business model, including the value proposition and customer segments, thus re-aligning the platform’s task to its evolved structure. Again, the role of the platform leader is a crucial aspect in setting the right boundaries to ensure the innovation of the platform’s business model. Moreover, such reciprocal adaptation of task and structure gradually occurs over time as a result of the continuous balance between pressures from the external context and from the platform’s stakeholders, and of the co-evolution of both social and technical aspects. Here, one key aspect emerges, ensuring the platform’s success and sustainability with respect to competitors. Such aspect is the evolvability of the platform over time, which is opposite to other competitors’ business models characterised by higher rigidity.

Proposition 2. In order to be successful and maintain a competitive position in the market, a digital multi-sided platform should have a flexible enough structure to adapt to a changing environment and incorporate in a coherent way such changes, always aligning the platform structure and task and achieve a constant and sustained evolution over time.

Fig. 4. Grounded model showing the interplay between the 2nd Order Themes and the relationships among them expressed in each proposition.

5.3. Opportunities offered by digital technologies

According to Kapoor et al. (2021), it is still not clear what are the determinants of network effects and incentives that will lead to better orchestration of platform's stakeholders. Actors build, use, and change the technology components to fulfil their business tasks, while technology components enable, facilitate, and constrain such business tasks. These interactions among actors and technology components occur over time and continuously change the business model (Haki, 2021).

The advancement of a platform's digitalisation and technological offering contributes to the strengthening of customers' digital competencies and enables the creation of new partnerships, thus establishing long-term relationships and increasing communication transparency between actors (Amaral & Orsato, 2022). Creating such a network of partners is important especially when a business model innovation occurs (see for instance the evolution of Regusto from B2C to B2B). Indeed, as the business model evolves, it enables the activation of positive externalities thanks to the existence of well-orchestrated value creation networks where each partner wins are critical for the platform's success in a B2B context (Hasler, Krumay, & Schallmo, 2022), thus enabling increasingly economically sustainable win-win configuration for the platform and its customers.

However, our findings suggest that technology is not the only component that explains the business model evolution and justifies the inclusion of new actors to meet the platform's and customers' evolving needs. Leveraging the opportunities offered by digital technologies does not solely result in greater economic sustainability. Indeed, it fosters social, economic, and environmental value creation and it supports business model innovation, confirming that digital technologies enable novel sustainable business models (Gregori & Holzmann, 2020). Nevertheless, little is known about the influence of the evolution of endogenous sustainability dimensions of a multi-sided platform on the platform's ability to leverage digital opportunities. Our results suggest that to strengthen the technological core by leveraging opportunities offered by digital technologies, a platform should include different sustainability dimensions and objectives, integrating sustainability dimensions, according to the TBL, with the technological one in the business model value proposition.

Proposition 3a. From a platform structure perspective, opportunities offered by digital technologies facilitate the creation of novel sustainable business and strengthen the platform's technological core.

Proposition 3b. From a platform network perspective, the integration of digital technologies at the business model level strengthens stakeholders' digital competencies and enables the creation of new partnerships.

5.4. Sustainability implications

So far, the literature lacks a clear understanding of the role of sustainability in multi sided platform's business models. In the business model literature, the role played by external contextual factors (e.g., change in competitive environment or and opportunities brought about by new information and communication technologies) on business model innovation has been already underlined (Saebi, Lien, & Foss, 2017). We build on this literature by arguing that contextual factors should be paired with exogenous sustainability requirements to achieve a comprehensive view of the external drivers impacting the sustainable business model innovation process. It is only when exogenous sustainability requirements are internalised and integrated by the platform leader within the business model that sustainability actually constitutes the value proposition. Considering the business model, we argue that the SBMI of a multi-sided platform has to take into account the mutual influence that exists between the evolution of endogenous sustainability dimensions, business model innovation, and the opportunities offered by digital technologies. The interplay between business model

innovation, endogenous sustainability dimensions and the leveraging of digital technologies opportunities has consequences in ensuring shared benefits for all the platform's stakeholders. Moreover, the factors that attract and keep customers should not only be attributed to pricing strategy and economic benefits. Instead, the progressive layering of sustainability dimensions at the business model level results in increased sustainability performance with mutually beneficial effects for both customers and the platform itself. Therefore, our conceptual framework sheds light on the key role of sustainability that has thus far been overlooked, thus contributing to the literature on digital multi-sided platforms and on the evolution of their business models over time.

Proposition 4. Sustainability, according to a TBL perspective, has the potential to increase the benefits for both the platform leader and its customers, thus strengthening the network effects and the incentives that enable value capture for all stakeholders.

6. Contributions, conclusions and future developments

This study explored the sustainable business model innovation process of a digital multi-sided platform. The platform evolved over time to balance the goals of long-term economic sustainability and avoiding food and non-food product waste, thus addressing social and environmental sustainability concerns. The contribution of this paper is both theoretical and empirical.

We contribute to the research on multi-sided platforms (de Reuver et al., 2018; Trabucchi et al., 2020; Trabucchi & Buganza, 2020) specifically in the B2B sector (Hasler et al., 2022; Loux et al., 2020), and more in detail targeting non-profit organisations (Mazzucchelli et al., 2021), where studies are scarcer. Second, As far as we know, our paper is one of the first taking into account the dimension of evolvability in the context of digital multi-sided platforms, given the longitudinal nature of our case study, thus overcoming the current lack of attention to longitudinal, process-based case studies on digital multi-sided platforms (Haki, 2021). Following the methodology of Gioia et al. (2013), we provide insights on the evolution of a multi-sided platform, contributing to the body of literature on business model innovation (Demil & Lecocq, 2010). In particular, we contribute to the theory on sustainable business model innovation (Bocken et al., 2014; Geissdoerfer, 2018) in the context of digital multi-sided platforms. Furthermore, by adopting a sociotechnical perspective of digital platforms (as suggested by Haki, 2021 and Kapoor et al., 2021) we investigated the dynamics of co-evolution existing among the platform's stakeholders and its technological components. Through such perspective we move beyond a merely technical, economical, and architectural understanding of digital multi-sided platforms (de Reuver et al., 2018; Tiwana, 2015). Accordingly, we show the close interrelation existing not only among the social side of a platform and its technological components, but also among the sustainability perspective, from a triple bottom line perspective and contextual factors. Specifically, we illustrate that social and environmental sustainability and digitalisation can trigger a virtuous cycle at the business model level that guarantees and the achievement of economic sustainability that allows platforms to survive rapidly-changing markets. As a result of our coding, we provide a theoretical framework that seeks to illuminate the dynamics existing among the process of sustainable business model innovation, its external drivers, and the resulting benefits for the platform's stakeholders, underlining the fundamental role of the platform leader in guiding such evolution.

As far as we know, this is the first study that integrates the perspective of sustainability into the sociotechnical theory in the context of digital platforms, especially when considering the literature of food loss and waste prevention and reduction through digital technologies, which is usually atheoretical (Trevisan & Formentini, 2023). Sociotechnical theory proves to be a good lens for investigating sustainability challenges. Indeed, sociotechnical systems should be addressed and adapted to pursue socially, economic, and environmentally sustainable

outcomes (Savaget, Geissdoerfer, Kharrazi, & Evans, 2019). Such change inevitably involves a multitude of different actors, processes, and technologies, and also implies a mediation among their frequently conflicting goals. Finally, our contribution furthers the discussion about the often controversial topic of environmental and social credit trading enabled by blockchain based multi-sided platforms, which is only partially addressed in the literature (Fernando, Tseng, Wahyuni-TD, Sroufe, & Mohd-Zailani, 2022) and usually focused on carbon credits (Liu & Zhang, 2019).

We then provide practical implications especially concerning sustainability, in alignment with the triple bottom line, and we suggest further implications for policymakers and for municipalities. Our case proves that supporting non-profit entities and subjects in need, as well as addressing urgent problems like food and non-food waste, can generate tangible social and environmental impacts able to directly increase benefits for a multi-sided ecosystem. We then show how the measurement of different types of sustainability performance and relative impacts can be a driver for achieving economic sustainability and innovating business models. In turn, this benefits customers by providing them with transparent CSR reporting. In light of these findings, we stress the importance of regulatory agencies designing appropriate policies and incentives for shaping adequate sustainability requirements. We finally highlight the implications for municipalities, who represent the non-transactional side of the platform and could benefit from access to the platform’s data and information, especially in reducing the costs for public administration of managing the food emergency and indirect losses resulting from the disruption of supply chains during the Covid-19 pandemic. Further, there are benefits for the citizens residing within their territory in terms of prevention and reduction of different kinds of waste (i.e., food, furniture, electronic products, domestic appliances, etc.), as well as changes to territorial fiscal policies based on the quantities donated, which could lead to reductions in waste taxation.

Our implications are not limited to the platforms for food surplus redistribution, as it’s the evolution of Regusto towards the redistribution of non-food items demonstrates. Therefore, we believe that our

theoretical framework has cross-context applicability (Busse, Kach, & Wagner, 2017), for other similar platforms across different contexts and markets. For instance, a business model based on the exchange of sustainability credits could be implemented in other contexts, given the growing demand and policy pressure for achieving net zero emissions and circularity. We are thus assisting the emergence of countless digital multi-sided platforms in the market, especially operating in the peer-to-peer sector (e.g., Vinted, Wallapop, and other platforms for promoting the consumption of second-hand goods). However, their social and environmental sustainability goals are frequently blurred and rarely supported by accurate measurements. Moreover, their business models often appear static, with limited space for evolution and innovation upstream in the supply chain, thus leading us to seriously question their ability to cope with the continuously changing business environment and their ability to achieve economic robustness. These limitations may present practitioners with the motivation for exploring alternative business models of digital multi-sided platforms in the B2B context.

Limitations of this work open up avenues for further research: other waste-intensive industries (e.g., the fashion industry), could be improved by studying existing multi-sided platforms operating in the B2B market with business model similar to the one addressed in this paper. Or future studies could introduce new business model, and test the validity of our theoretical framework in different contexts. Finally, as our study is qualitative, additional efforts in exploring the relationships among the emerged themes quantitatively might lead to interesting results.

Data availability

The data that has been used is confidential.

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Appendix

Table A1

Data table with representative quotes supporting the 1st Order Codes and 2nd Order Themes.

2nd Order Themes	1st Order Concepts	Representative quotes
(a) <i>Business model innovation</i>	(1) <i>Evolution of the customer segments and of customer relationships over time</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “The platform’s customers were initially food services selling surplus food and private customers buying it. After the evolution to the B2B model, companies, municipalities and charities were the new customer segments. Such customers remained unchanged, what changed was their relationship with the platform” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “Having municipalities on board may increase the platform’s credibility and reliability at the first stages of development” (Informant 2). • “With the recent innovation of the business model, we distinguish among donors and credits acquirers” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “The initial goal was to provide a paid service for municipalities and free for companies and non-profit organisations, but this become an issue specially after Covid-19 which weighted on municipalities expenses, therefore the current model is based on companies that are paying a fee on the kg of product transacted” (Co-founder of Regusto).
	(2) <i>Evolution of the economic model</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “The initial model was based on the payment of a fee on the food surplus from food services acquired by private customers [...] the new model aims to monetise the impact detected and measured through indicators turning it into credits” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “The aim is to reach the economic sustainability of the platforms by selling credits, thus monetising the value created by avoiding food waste and reducing social and environmental impact” (Co-founder of Regusto).
	(3) <i>Extension of the platform’s scope</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Initially we addressed B2C market segment in the profit sector, later the business model extended to the non-profit B2B to manage the donation of food surpluses, involving charities” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “A further development of the business model took place in 2021, with the extension to the management of non-food products” (Co-founder of Regusto).
(b) <i>Leveraging opportunities offered by digital technologies</i>	(4) <i>Digitalisation as a business model pillar</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Since the beginning Regusto aimed at leveraging its digital assets and competences for enabling an innovative business model. Companies have recognised this feature of Regusto and they appreciate the possibility of managing digitally the donation process end-to-end,

(continued on next page)

Table A1 (continued)

2nd Order Themes	1st Order Concepts	Representative quotes
(c) Evolution of endogenous sustainability dimensions	(5) Introduction of blockchain to enable transparency and traceability of transactions	<p>when, in most cases, such a process was previously managed manually” (Co-founder of Regusto).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “A service offered by Regusto and of extreme importance is the digitisation and tracking of donation flows, indeed, our company did not use applications for tracking such flow before starting the partnership with Regusto” (Informant 5). • “Although blockchain is an important element which contributes to reinforce the digitalisation of the platform, it is not a key enabler of the business model” (Informant 1). • “The desire to choose Regusto is also motivated by the use of blockchain which allows to obtain great value not only in terms of certified and transparent operations, but also in terms of brand image” (Informant 4). • “We noticed that our clients were demanding higher standards in terms of transactions transparency, security and reliability, thus we introduced blockchain technology” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “It is important that the data source is verified and certified. At the moment data are certified by RSM international, but it is expected to start a new collaboration with Certiquality” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “Blockchain technology ensures transaction` transparency and traceability, as it is a decentralised blockchain. Decentralisation makes the blockchain secure because if one node is interrupted, there are other players that guarantee and confirm that type of data. The value of the blockchain is decentralisation” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “Generally, a business model is independent from blockchain, but blockchain is very important when performing donations transactions and automatically generate an NFT token which corresponds to one credit” (Informant 1).
	(6) Blockchain for credits-based business model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Blockchain is becoming more and more important for Regusto, especially for the new business model entirely based on credits. One credit is in fact an NFT token, exactly like carbon credits” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “Our first aim was to contrast food waste through food surplus redistribution, we were aware of the social and environmental impact related to the food waste issue, but we were not measuring in detail such impact yet” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “The platform started addressing social sustainability dimension by donating food collected to charities” (Co-founder of Regusto).
	(7) Evolution of social and environmental sustainability dimensions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “A first indicator was developed to calculate the quantity of food donated in terms of number of donated meals” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “The environmental impact of food donation is calculated in terms of avoided CO₂ emissions and avoided consumption of water and soil” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “The calculation of the impact indices is carried out in partnerships with universities and specialised partners. Now we count 18 environmental and social impact indicators” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “We started with the redistribution of the food surplus, subsequently the impacts generated were monitored and measured, offering additional services to firms, and today we want to monetize on the positive environmental and social impacts generated through credits: we want to give value to an already virtuous cycle in itself, adding the element of economic sustainability (at the beginning it was a latent need, then it is understood that credit brings a contribution of economic margin and visibility)” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “Our priority now is to find a business model which is financially robust and sustainable, still relying on our core value of sustainability” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “The goal is to make the platform free for all users and to exploit the value generated by food donation that will autonomously support the platform” (Co-founder of Regusto). <p>See also the “(2) Evolution of the economic model” code.</p>
	(8) Evolution of economic sustainability dimension	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “The entrance in the market of a strong competitor with a comparable business model and, afterwards, the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic are two factors that have led to an evolution of the platform business model. We decided to suspend the app due to the crisis affecting the food service sector, while greater importance was given to the non-profit sector. After the pandemic, the platform tool for addressing the B2B sector was finally adopted, in order to respond to food requirements deriving from the health emergency” (Co-founder of Regusto).
	(9) Market competition and Covid-19 pandemic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “We define Municipalities as passive actors since they do not pay anymore for accessing the platform but they can take advantage of the data collected and monitor the exchange flows that take place on their territory. This change was introduced after the pandemic, as municipalities had fewer resources available and were experiencing increasing organisational difficulties” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “We joined the platform thanks to the collaboration with policymakers which led the extension of the <i>Gadda law 166/16</i> for food donations, also to non-food products” (Informant 3).
	Contextual factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “We are planning to adopt the blockchain provided by Algorand which is in line with our objective of lowering impact on the environment” (Co-founder of Regusto).
	(10) The role of municipalities after the pandemic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Companies are measuring the impacts through indicators and provide transparent data to make a certified environmental sustainability report to avoid green washing. There are no formal requirements for the CSR budget or report in our case, but many competitors are choosing to do it, therefore we need to overcome competition” (Informant 6). • “The desire to associate with Regusto was therefore born to respond to a new need in terms of communication, to precisely measure the sustainability indices and to effectively manage the tracking of donations” (Informant 4).
	(11) Higher sustainability standards are required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “One of the main benefits of Regusto is the speed of finding third sector clients for quickly donating surplus products” (Informant 3).
	Sustainability requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “The desire to associate with Regusto was therefore born to respond to a new need in terms of communication, to precisely measure the sustainability indices and to effectively manage the tracking of donations” (Informant 4).
	(12) Need to avoid greenwashing and provide transparent data for sustainability reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “One of the main benefits of Regusto is the speed of finding third sector clients for quickly donating surplus products” (Informant 3).
	Enhanced technological performance and competences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “One of the main benefits of Regusto is the speed of finding third sector clients for quickly donating surplus products” (Informant 3).

(continued on next page)

Table A1 (continued)

2nd Order Themes	1st Order Concepts	Representative quotes
Mutually beneficial increased sustainability performance	(14) Tracking and managing donation flows	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Regusto allows our company to access donations from new suppliers frequently coming from a different city or region, therefore Regusto has played an important role in creating contacts with new companies and reinforcing existing partnerships” (Informant 5). • “A service offered by Regusto and of extreme importance is the digitisation and tracking of donation flows, indeed, our company did not use applications for tracking such flow before starting the partnership with Regusto” (Informant 5). • “Since the beginning Regusto aimed at leveraging its digital assets and competences for enabling an innovative business model. Companies have recognised this feature of Regusto and they appreciate the possibility of managing digitally the donation process end-to-end, when, in most cases, such a process was previously managed manually” (Co-founder of Regusto). • “The platform has ensured greater ease of managing relationships with partners and donors. For example, on the occasion of a donation from Moleskine, our company met a transportation company partner of Moleskine which expressed the need to dispose of surplus stocks, including non-food items. Regusto therefore made it possible to create a new partnership that would bring value to both actors involved in order to generate value from surpluses” (Informant 2).
	(15) Ease of finding new donors and donations recipients quickly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Our company started a collaboration with the Regusto platform in 2021, after the elaboration of a new corporate sustainability strategy based on four pillars, which are our core values. The choice of joining Regusto was indeed in line with our social and environmental sustainability values and it represented a win-win-win solution for us, for the platform and for the charities” (Informant 4). • “The most important data for us regards the calculation of credits, especially CO₂ impacts and donated meals” (Informant 3).
	(16) Measuring and monitoring sustainability performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Our company started a collaboration with the Regusto platform in 2021, after the elaboration of a new corporate sustainability strategy based on four pillars, which are our core values. The choice of joining Regusto was in line with our social and environmental sustainability values and it represented a win-win-win solution for us, for the platform and for the charities” (Informant 4). • “The value of using the platform consists especially of the data related to the impact of donations in terms of equivalent meals, which is an information easy to communicate even outside the company” (Informant 2). • “Having visibility on donation flows in our municipality is crucial since it gives us the possibility of building a comprehensive picture of solidarity and circularity initiatives in our territory, as well as promoting such initiatives also outside our territory borders, and design specific policies which is relevant nowadays especially with water savings and CO₂.” (Informant 7).
	(17) Gain visibility over donations flow in a municipality	

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